

Qualitative Analysis of a Mixture of Ferrocyanide, Ferricyanide and Thiocyanate.

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Two methods are now generally employed for the qualitative analysis of a mixture of ferrocyanide, ferricyanide and thiocyanate. Of these, one depends on the use of iron salts while the other devised by Browning and Palmer (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, **54**, 315) requires solutions of thorium nitrate and cadmium chloride for the separation of ferro- and ferri-cyanide respectively. The second method, though it gives fairly good results, presents some difficulties in the course of filtration, thorium ferrocyanide and cadmium ferricyanide, being in a very fine state of division, easily pass through the filter paper.

The object of the present investigation was to see whether the salts of common metals can be used in place of thorium nitrate. But on studying the solubilities of different ferro- and ferri-cyanide, it has been observed that the metals which give insoluble ferrocyanides also give insoluble ferricyanides. So it is not possible to separate the two acids with the help of these salts.

It has, however, been found that if cerous nitrate whose ferrocyanide is insoluble (100 gms. of water dissolving 0.0017 gm. of cerous ferrocyanide at 21°) is used in place of thorium nitrate, a more granular precipitate of cerous ferrocyanide is formed which can be easily filtered and washed in a comparatively shorter time. On the other hand ferricyanide can be better precipitated as nickel ferricyanide (a substance quite insoluble in water), with a solution of nickel nitrate, which, though a little difficult to wash on account of its gelatinous character, does not pass through the filter paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

In actual analysis 5-10 c.c. of a neutral solution containing potassium ferrocyanide, potassium ferricyanide and potassium thiocyanate were treated in the cold with a solution of cerous nitrate ("Kahlbaum" refined) which gave a crystalline granular precipitate of

cerous ferrocyanide $\text{CeKFe}(\text{CN})_6$ (Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 1353). The precipitate was washed with cold water, treated with a little sodium hydroxide solution on the filter paper to decompose the ferrocyanide and to have some sodium ferrocyanide in the filtrate. The solution thus obtained was acidified with hydrochloric acid, and a few drops of ferric chloride were added to it when the formation of Prussian blue indicated the presence of ferrocyanide.

The filtrate left after the separation of ferrocyanide was treated with a slight excess of nickel nitrate when nickel ferricyanide $\text{Ni}_3[\text{FeCy}_6]_2, 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was precipitated. The precipitate was, as before, washed with cold water, treated with sodium hydroxide solution to get some sodium ferricyanide, the filtrate acidified and a few drops of ferrous sulphate solution added to it. Formation of Turnbull's blue showed the presence of ferricyanogen ion.

Thiocyanate was detected in the filtrate left after the separation of ferricyanide by adding a few drops of ferric chloride.

Some of the experimental results are shown in the following tables.

TABLE I.

Concentration of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.	Concentration of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.	Concentration of KCNS.	Reaction for $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.
0.01 gm.	0.1 gm.	0.1 ..	Quite distinct.
0.005 ..	0.1 ..	0.1 ..	..
0.001 ..	0.1 ..	0.1 ..	..
0.0005 ..	0.1 ..	0.1 ..	Distinct.
0.0002 ..	0.1 ..	0.1 ..	Faint.
0.0001 ..	0.1 ..	0.1 ..	Very faint.

TABLE II.

Concentration of $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.	Concentration of $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.	Concentration of KCNS.	Reaction for $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$.
0.1 gm.	0.001 gm.	0.1 gm.	Distinct.
0.1 ..	0.0005 ..	0.1 ..	..
0.1 ..	0.0002 ..	0.1 ..	..
0.1 ..	0.0001 ..	0.1 ..	..

TABLE III.

Concentration of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Concentration of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$.	Concentration of KCNS.	Reaction for KCNS.
0.1 gm.	0.1 gm.	0.001 gm.	Quite sharp.
0.1 "	0.1 "	0.0005 "	"
0.1 "	0.1 "	0.0002 "	Faint.
0.1 "	0.1 "	0.0001 "	"

When the quantity of thiocyanate is very small, the green colour of the nickel salt tends to interfere with the red coloration produced by ferric chloride and potassium thiocyanate. So in Table III, with 0.0002 and 0.0001 gm. of thiocyanate, a faint coloration was obtained. This difficulty can however be removed by separating the nickel with a little sodium hydroxide solution before adding ferric chloride to it.

TABLE IV.

Concentration of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$.	Concentration of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$.	Concentration of KCNS.	Reaction for $K_4Fe(CN)_6$, $K_3Fe(CN)_6$. KCNS.
0.01 gm.	0.01 gm.	0.01 gm.	Sharp reactions for all the three.
0.005 "	0.005 "	0.005 "	"
0.001 "	0.001 "	0.001 "	"
0.0005 "	0.0005 "	0.0005 "	"

Ferricyanide can also be detected after the separation of ferrocyanide, by reducing it with some reducing agent, such as alkaline hydrazine sulphate or hydroxylamine hydrochloride and then precipitating it again as ferrocyanide.

The solution, after the separation of ferrocyanide with an excess of cerous nitrate, was reduced with an ammoniacal solution of hydrazine sulphate or hydroxylamine hydrochloride until it became almost perfectly colourless.* A white precipitate of cerous ferrocyanide was at once formed by the excess of cerous nitrate already present in

* Reduction can also be carried out by making the solution strongly alkaline with caustic soda or potash and then adding ferrous sulphate or better, manganous or cobaltous chloride ("Cyanogen Compounds," H. E. Williams).

the solution. Some more cerous nitrate was added so as to make the precipitation complete. This was filtered, washed and analysed as usual. Cerous ferrocyanide formed at this stage may contain a little cerous hydroxide on account of the presence of free ammonia, but it does no harm. Thiocyanate was detected in the filtrate, after acidifying it with hydrochloric acid, with a few drops of ferric chloride.

A few results are given below :—

Concentration of $K_2Fe(CN)_6$.	Concentration of $K_3Fe(CN)_6$.	Concentration of KCNS.	Reaction for $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ and KCNS..
0.1 gm.	0.01 gm.	0.01 gm.	Quite sharp.
0.1 ..	0.001 ..	0.001 ..	
0.1 ..	0.0005 ..	0.0005 ..	

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